

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOUSSA YAYE****FIRST NAME: ABDOULAYE****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: Six (6)****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE

1. What is the main topic of the course offered in this fourth edition of ACA-401

Coursepack?

Professional writing.¹

Essay writing.

Introduction to academic writing at Euclid University.

The difference between American and British English.

2. What is the purpose mentioned for reviewing student work in this ACA-401

Coursepack course?

Help students understand the corrections made.²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 3.

² Ibid.

- Grading assignments without giving feedback.
- Encourage students to copy other student's answers.

3. What is research?

- Answering a question by obtaining information.**³
- A systematic research process to answer a question.
- Relying on facts shared and accepted by all as truths independent of one's feelings and beliefs.
- Learning to use and judge others' research.

4. What form is best for graphically presenting complex data?

- The graphic form that best achieves the desired effect.**⁴
- A table.
- A bar chart
- Line graph

5. Please let me know when you should provide a citation.

- When you want to protect yourself from plagiarism.**⁵
- When you are not taking credit for work that is not your own.
- When you want to engage others in new directions.
- When you are not taking credit for work that is not your own.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

⁴ Ibid., 87.

⁵ Ibid., 140.

6. What are the characteristics of Date-Author Style?
- Sign the source by placing a quotation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) beside your reference.⁶**
 - Indicate the source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence you quote or refer to.
 - Report the source by placing a citation next to your reference.
 - List sources at the end of the document in a bibliography
7. What is the purpose of the literature review?
- Find out has already been done in relation to your topic.⁷**
 - To help the reader understand the variables examined in the thesis.
 - Help the reader understand the variables that will be examined in the thesis and justify the research questions that will be asked.
 - To provide the necessary contextual or conceptual background to enable the reader to critique the discussion as soon as the results are analyzed.
8. Why discuss thesis results?
- To assess whether the research advances theory and practice.⁸**
 - Provide an interpretation of the thesis research findings in the context of the literature review.
 - Present the most satisfying, enjoyable, and significant aspect of the thesis research.

⁶ Ibid., 142.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 355.

⁸ Ibid., 63.

- To help understand the significance of the theory and research results presented.
9. What is the punctuation rule that a text must respect in English according to the regulations of the European Union?
- Punctuation marks in English are always, except hyphens and ellipsis dots close to the preceding Word, letter, or number, followed by a single space.**⁹
- Full stops are always followed by a single space, not a double space.
- A single space always follows full stops.
- Ellipsis dots are close to the preceding Word, letter, or number.
10. What is the legal personality of the European Union in treaties and legislation?
- European Union.**¹⁰
- European Community.
- Union.
- EU.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide* (European Commission, 2021), 9.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 73.

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